

When Forgetting Fails: Characterizing Class Unlearning Failure Modes in Non-IID Decentralized Federated Learning

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Abstract—Gossip-based decentralized federated learning (DFL) achieves generalization through iterative pairwise weight averaging, propagating learned representations across all nodes regardless of local data composition. This same mechanism creates a structural failure mode for class unlearning: gossip convergence drives all nodes toward a shared consensus model, so every node’s weights encode forget-class knowledge irrespective of local shard composition, yet each must erase it using only local gradient signal. Naïve gradient-ascent unlearning fails disproportionately across nodes under non-IID Dirichlet-partitioned data, appearing to succeed by global forget-class accuracy while leaving measurable per-node membership-inference disparity that grows monotonically with heterogeneity. We term this the *gossip convergence unlearning paradox* and show that per-node MIA AUC variance and per-node L2 distance to a FedRetrain baseline are necessary verification metrics that global means conceal. At extreme concentration ($\alpha = 0.1$), zero-sample nodes present a structural verification problem: they cannot supply local members for MIA evaluation yet encode the forget-class representation as completely as any other node. We propose Class-Frequency-Aware Unlearning (CFAU), a fully adaptive protocol requiring no inter-node communication beyond standard gossip rounds, and validate all findings on a physical six-node Raspberry Pi Zero 2W cluster executing pure NumPy gradient computation on CIFAR-10 under IID and Dirichlet $\alpha \in \{1.0, 0.5, 0.1\}$. Statistical scaling is validated on an extended 30-node cluster, confirming that σ_{MIA} scales monotonically with heterogeneity (0.024 IID \rightarrow 0.063 at $\alpha = 0.1$) and that 21 of 30 nodes are structurally excluded from MIA verification at extreme concentration. CFAU reduces per-node MIA variance by 24–36% under moderate heterogeneity at no additional wall-clock cost relative to naïve interleaved.

Index Terms—decentralized federated learning, machine unlearning, gossip protocols, non-IID data, membership inference, edge computing, Raspberry Pi, privacy-preserving machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Edge deployments of machine learning, distributed sensing networks, smart home systems and personal health monitors increasingly require the ability to remove learned categories from deployed models without retraining from scratch. A sensing network that must cease recognizing a withdrawn data category or a deployment of IoT devices that must drop a class whose data collection has been discontinued, cannot afford to retrain collaboratively from scratch after every such request: on resource-constrained hardware with no persistent uplink,

retraining is computationally prohibitive. The broader regulatory context of frameworks including GDPR [1] and CCPA [2] establishes rights to data erasure and further motivates efficient unlearning mechanisms, though the operational deployment scenarios above are the immediate driver of the class-level granularity studied here.

In fully decentralized federated learning (DFL) [3], IoT nodes train collaboratively via peer-to-peer gossip with no central aggregator, achieving resilience to single-point failure and natural adaptation to dynamic network topologies [3], [4], properties increasingly attractive as machine learning moves to the network edge [5], [6]. Yet this serverless architecture is incompatible with the assumption underlying most federated unlearning work, which relies on a central parameter server to coordinate gradient updates or redistribute retraining workloads [7], [8], an assumption that excludes the growing class of deployments where maintaining a persistent uplink to a central aggregator is impractical [3], [9]. Recent server-free approaches address client-level removal in decentralized settings: HDUS [10] via seed model distillation and PDUOT [11] via gradient residual approximation under dynamic topologies. However, neither addresses the class-skew heterogeneity that arises when gossip mixing distributes class knowledge to nodes holding zero local samples of the forget class. This failure mode has not previously been characterized.

In gossip-based DFL, knowledge propagation is the mechanism of training: through repeated weight averaging across neighbors [12], [13], every node in a converged system holds a model encoding information from every other node’s local data. When a class unlearning request arrives, every node must therefore erase the forget-class representation, yet each must do so using only its own local gradient signal, with no coordinator to redistribute forget-class updates from nodes that hold relevant data. We term this the *gossip convergence unlearning paradox*: a universal forgetting obligation paired with strictly local erasure capacity.

Under non-IID Dirichlet partitioning [14], this mismatch manifests with particular severity. As α decreases, forget-class data concentrates on a small subset of nodes while gossip convergence simultaneously drives all nodes to encode equivalent representations, so every node must erase the same knowledge from gradient signal ranging from dozens of local samples to none. This asymmetry is invisible to global verification metrics: a system reporting acceptable mean MIA AUC [15], [16] or mean L2 distance to a FedRetrain baseline [17], [7] may nonetheless contain nodes retaining significant

forget-class membership signal. Worse, zero-sample nodes, those most in need of verification, are the least verifiable by membership inference, since MIA requires local forget-class training samples they do not possess.

The principal contributions of this work are as follows. First, to our knowledge this is the first empirical characterization of class unlearning in a physical gossip-based DFL system, validating that the interaction between gossip convergence and non-IID data partitioning produces systematic unlearning failure modes under genuine edge hardware constraints. Second, we identify and formally characterize the gossip convergence unlearning paradox and establish that per-node MIA score variance and per-node L2 distance to a FedRetrain baseline [18] are necessary verification metrics that global means conceal, as zero-sample nodes present a structural verification problem precisely because they hold no local forget-class data to supply membership inference evaluation. The statistical scaling of this failure mode is validated on an extended 30-node cluster, where σ_{MIA} scales monotonically from 0.024 at IID to 0.063 at $\alpha = 0.1$ and 21 of 30 nodes are structurally excluded from MIA verification at extreme concentration. Third, we propose CFAU, a fully adaptive unlearning protocol requiring no inter-node communication beyond standard gossip rounds, and validate it on physical edge hardware under genuine resource constraints across four data heterogeneity conditions.

II. RELATED WORK

Table I summarizes the landscape of related work across five capability dimensions.

A. Machine Unlearning Foundations

Cao and Yang [18] frame removal as an algebraic operation on summation-form learning algorithms. Bourtole et al. introduce SISA training [19], reducing retraining cost through data sharding; certified unlearning is studied by Sekhari et al. via Newton-step updates [20] and Guo et al. via influence-function removal [21]. All four methods assume centralized access to model and data, a condition that does not hold in the server-free gossip topology studied here.

B. MIA and Weight Norm Verification

Shokri et al. establish membership inference as a practical privacy verification tool [16]; Yeom et al. introduce the loss-threshold formulation used here [15], applied independently at each node and evaluated via AUC to account for class imbalance. No existing federated or decentralized unlearning work reports per-node MIA variance as a verification metric. Its absence means the local failure mode we characterize has not previously been detectable, let alone addressed.

C. Federated Unlearning

FedEraser [7] stores historical checkpoints server-side to calibrate unlearning updates; FedCIO [23] achieves exact unlearning via server-coordinated two-phase protocol; FedRecovery [24] removes a client’s influence by subtracting a server-aggregated weighted sum of gradient residuals from the global

model, providing differentially private unlearning guarantees but requiring the server to cache the full gradient history and reporting only global verification metrics. Li et al. propose a teacher-student active forgetting framework [22] at class granularity that eliminates dependence on historical updates but assumes central aggregation and does not examine per-node heterogeneity as a failure mechanism. A common thread across all these works is server-side orchestration, storing historical state, coordinating unlearning rounds, or performing global aggregation, which is architecturally incompatible with the server-free gossip topology studied here.

D. Decentralized and Gossip-Based Federated Learning

Lian et al. establish that decentralized parallel stochastic gradient descent [13] can match or outperform centralized SGD in communication efficiency, providing the convergence foundation on which gossip-based federated learning builds. Gossip learning eliminates the central server through iterative peer-to-peer model averaging [25]. PDUOT [11] provides provable client-level unlearning guarantees under dynamic topologies without additional communication or retraining, but operates at client granularity only, does not examine non-IID heterogeneity as a failure mechanism, and provides no per-node empirical verification. Ye et al. propose HDUS [10], a decentralized unlearning framework built on knowledge distillation rather than gossip weight averaging, which avoids weight-space erasure entirely by isolating neighbor knowledge in distilled seed models rather than fusing it into each node’s main model; unlearning reduces to removing a seed model from the local ensemble, achieving exact client-level unlearning without retraining. This architectural choice sidesteps the gossip convergence paradox but requires a shared 10,000-sample reference dataset and a GPU-class distillation pipeline, a resource profile incompatible with the memory-constrained edge devices studied here and does not address per-node heterogeneity as a failure mechanism. Our work occupies the intersection left vacant by both: class-level unlearning in a server-free gossip topology on physical edge hardware, with Dirichlet non-IID heterogeneity as the primary mechanism of failure.

E. Non-IID Heterogeneity as a Failure Mechanism

Non-IID distribution is widely treated as a performance variable in federated unlearning, evaluated across one or two heterogeneity configurations to observe graceful degradation. We take a structurally different position: Dirichlet concentration α is not a nuisance variable but the *mechanism* through which gossip-based unlearning fails, producing globally plausible forgetting metrics while residual memorization persists at the per-node level, a failure mode invisible to aggregate evaluation and unaddressed by any prior work.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Gossip-Based Decentralized Federated Learning

Let $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ denote the communication graph, where $\mathcal{V} = \{v_1, \dots, v_N\}$ is the set of N participating nodes and $\mathcal{E} \subseteq$

TABLE I

COMPARISON OF RELATED WORK AGAINST THIS PAPER’S CONTRIBUTIONS. ✓ = COVERED; △ = PARTIAL OR SIMULATED ONLY; — = NOT COVERED.

Work	ARCHITECTURE & SETTING			UNLEARNING METHOD		VERIFICATION & ANALYSIS			
	Gossip / DFL	Non-IID data	No central server	Sample unlearning	Class unlearning	Per-node MIA	Weight norm (L2) analysis	Failure mode analysis	Adaptive node weight
<i>Unlearning Foundations</i>									
Cao & Yang, 2015 [18]	—	—	—	✓	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Machine unlearning (summation form)</i>									
Bourtoule et al., 2021 [19]	—	—	—	✓	—	—	—	—	—
<i>SISA — sharded retraining</i>									
Sekhri et al., 2021 [20]	—	—	—	✓	—	—	—	—	—
<i>NeurIPS — certified unlearning</i>									
Guo et al., 2020 [21]	—	—	—	✓	—	—	—	—	—
<i>ICML — certified data removal</i>									
<i>MIA & Weight Norm Verification</i>									
Shokri et al., 2017 [16]	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Attack methodology used for verification in this work</i>									
Yeom et al., 2018 [15]	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Loss-threshold MIA</i>									
<i>Federated Unlearning</i>									
McMahan et al., 2017 [6]	—	△	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>FedAvg — centralised FL baseline</i>									
Liu et al., 2021 [7]	—	△	—	✓	—	—	—	—	—
<i>FedEraser — centralised FL sample unlearning</i>									
Li et al., 2025 [22]	—	△	—	—	✓	—	—	—	—
<i>Class-wise federated unlearning via active forgetting</i>									
FedCIO [23]	—	✓	—	✓	—	△	—	—	—
<i>Exact federated unlearning</i>									
Zhang et al., 2023 [24]	—	△	—	✓	—	—	✓	—	—
<i>FedRecovery — gradient residual federated unlearning</i>									
<i>Decentralised / Gossip FL</i>									
Hegedüs et al., 2019 [25]	✓	△	✓	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Gossip learning — decentralised FL comparison</i>									
Ye et al., 2024 [10]	△	△	✓	✓	—	—	—	—	—
<i>HDUS — seed-model ensemble decentralised unlearning</i>									
PDUOT, ICML 2025 [11]	✓	—	✓	✓	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Decentralised FL unlearning</i>									
<i>This Work</i>									
CFAU (ours)	✓	✓	✓	—	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Class-Frequency-Aware Unlearning</i>									

$\mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$ defines the peer links. Each node v_i holds a local dataset $\mathcal{D}_i = \{(x_j, y_j)\}$ drawn from a class-conditional distribution that may differ across nodes.

At each gossip round t , every node v_i performs one or more local gradient descent steps on $\theta_i^{(t)}$, then pushes weights to each peer $v_j \in \mathcal{N}(i)$. Upon receiving parameters from all peers, v_i updates via sample-count-weighted averaging:

$$\theta_i^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \frac{n_i \theta_i^{(t)} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} n_j \theta_j^{(t)}}{n_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} n_j} \quad (1)$$

where $n_i = |\mathcal{D}_i|$. Training continues for T rounds until convergence, at which point all nodes converge to the same parameters θ^* , with empirically confirmed $\text{std}(\text{acc}_i) = 0.000$ across all N nodes.

B. Non-IID Data Partitioning

Data heterogeneity is parameterised via the Dirichlet distribution. For C classes and N nodes, the proportion of class- c samples assigned to node v_i is drawn as:

$$\mathbf{p}^c \sim \text{Dir}(\alpha \cdot \mathbf{1}_N) \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha > 0$ is the concentration parameter ($\alpha \rightarrow \infty$: IID; $\alpha \rightarrow 0$: extreme heterogeneity). We evaluate $\alpha \in \{1.0, 0.5, 0.1\}$, corresponding to moderate, strong, and extreme heterogeneity. The local forget-class frequency at node v_i is:

$$f_i = \frac{|\mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{F}}|}{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{F}} \subseteq \mathcal{D}_i$ denotes the local forget-class subset, and $\bar{f} = 1/C$ is the IID reference frequency.

C. Class Unlearning Objective

Let $c^* \in \{0, \dots, C - 1\}$ denote the target forget class. A class unlearning algorithm \mathcal{U} takes the converged model θ^* and produces an unlearned model $\hat{\theta}$ statistically indistinguishable from a model retrained from scratch on the retain partition $\mathcal{D}^{\mathcal{R}} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) \in \mathcal{D}_i : y \neq c^*\}$. In the gossip setting, \mathcal{U} runs independently at each node v_i on its local data without inter-node communication during the unlearning phase.

D. Naive Unlearning Failure Conditions

The naive baseline applies gradient ascent on $\mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{F}}$ for a fixed T_{base} steps uniformly across all nodes regardless of f_i . Two failure conditions arise: when $f_i \gg \bar{f}$, a node receives insufficient ascent steps relative to its local memorization depth; when $f_i \approx 0$, a node that absorbed forget-class knowledge via gossip holds no local gradient signal to guide erasure. In both cases, residual membership signal persists at the node level while global aggregates remain within acceptable bounds.

E. Verification Protocol

Global metrics, specifically forget-class accuracy and test-set accuracy aggregated across nodes, are necessary but not sufficient for verifying unlearning completeness. Aggregation masks per-node residual memorization, motivating evaluation at the node level. **Per-node MIA AUC:** for each node v_i with $|\mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{F}}| > 0$, a loss-threshold attack [15] is applied using local forget-class training samples as members and held-out forget-class test samples as non-members. The variance $\sigma_{\text{MIA}} = \text{std}(\text{AUC}_i)$ across evaluable nodes is the primary signal of unlearning heterogeneity. **Weight norm correlation:** the Pearson correlation $r(\text{L2})$ between per-node L2 weight norm change $\|\hat{\theta}_i - \theta^*\|_2$ and f_i serves as a mechanistic indicator of effort distribution. Under naive unlearning, $r(\text{L2}) < 0$ indicates inverted effort; under CFAU, $r(\text{L2}) \approx +1$ indicates frequency-proportional effort.

IV. METHOD

A. Naive Unlearning Baseline

The naive baseline proceeds in three phases per unlearning round.

Phase 1 — Gradient ascent. Following the gradient-ascent unlearning primitive of Golatkar et al. [26], for T_{base} steps the loss on the local forget set is ascended:

$$\theta_i \leftarrow \theta_i + \eta_u \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta_i; \mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{F}}) \quad (4)$$

The step count T_{base} is fixed and uniform across all nodes, irrespective of f_i .

Phase 2 — Interleaved retain fine-tuning. A naive interleaved variant alternates gradient descent on the retain set with the ascent phase:

$$\theta_i \leftarrow \theta_i - \eta_f \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta_i; \mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{R}}) \quad (5)$$

Fine-tuning is applied once per ascent step ($K = 1$ uniformly). Nodes with fewer than n_{min} retain samples skip fine-tuning. A sequential variant applying all ascent steps before any fine-tuning is also evaluated as an additional reference point.

Phase 3 — Gossip propagation. After local unlearning, each node pushes updated parameters to peers via Eq. (1). All nodes complete Phases 1–2 before gossip resumes (synchronous unlearn-then-gossip), ensuring unlearning signals propagate without re-contamination. Phases 1–3 repeat for R unlearning rounds.

The critical limitation is that T_{base} is blind to f_i : nodes where $f_i \gg \bar{f}$ receive insufficient ascent steps, while nodes where $f_i \approx 0$ ascend on an effectively empty forget set regardless of gossip-absorbed knowledge they hold.

B. Class-Frequency-Aware Unlearning (CFAU)

CFAU corrects the uniform step-count assumption by scaling each node’s gradient ascent budget in proportion to local forget-class frequency relative to the IID expectation.

1) *Signal Routing:* The frequency weight at node v_i is:

$$w_i = \frac{f_i}{\bar{f}} = C \cdot f_i \quad (6)$$

Two conditions route the node to naive fallback:

$$\text{too-low: } f_i < \tau \cdot \bar{f} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{near-IID: } |w_i - 1| \leq \delta \quad (8)$$

The *too-low* condition ($\tau = 0.5$, i.e. $f_i < 0.05$) identifies nodes whose local frequency is below half the IID rate, where frequency-proportional scaling would reduce the step count below the naive baseline. The *near-IID* condition ($\delta = 0.15$, i.e. $w_i \in [0.85, 1.15]$) identifies nodes close enough to the IID expectation that scaling provides negligible benefit. Both conditions are evaluated locally from shard statistics; no inter-node communication is required. Nodes satisfying either condition fall back to naive with $T_i = T_{\text{base}}$; all others proceed through CFAU scaling.

2) *Adaptive Step Count:* For nodes routed to CFAU:

$$T_i = \min(\text{round}(T_{\text{base}} \cdot w_i), T_{\text{max}}) \quad (9)$$

where $T_{\text{max}} = 2 \times T_{\text{base}}$, a ceiling confirmed empirically as the boundary beyond which fixed η_u causes model destabilization. Any node with f_i low enough to produce $T_i < T_{\text{base}}$ is already caught by the too-low routing condition and redirected to fallback before scaling is applied. Table IV reports the resulting per-node step counts across all experimental conditions.

3) *Self-Tuned Interleaved Fine-Tuning:* The interleave interval $K_i = \max(1, \text{round}(w_i))$ is derived directly from w_i , requiring no additional hyperparameter. Because both T_i and K_i scale with w_i , their ratio $T_i/K_i \approx T_{\text{base}}$ remains approximately constant across nodes: high-concentration nodes receive more ascent steps but fine-tune proportionally less often, preserving total utility-recovery effort independent of local concentration. Algorithm 1 gives the complete per-node execution.

Algorithm 1 CFAU: Per-Node Execution at Node v_i

Require: $\theta_i \leftarrow \theta^*$, $\mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{F}}$, $\mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{R}}$, T_{base} , T_{max} , τ , δ , η_u , η_f , n_{min} , R

Ensure: $\hat{\theta}_i$

- 1: $f_i \leftarrow |\mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{F}}| / |\mathcal{D}_i|$
- 2: $w_i \leftarrow C \cdot f_i$
- 3: **if** $f_i < \tau \cdot \bar{f}$ **or** $|w_i - 1| \leq \delta$ **then**
- 4: $T_i \leftarrow T_{\text{base}}$; $K_i \leftarrow 1$ {naive fallback; fine-tune every step}
- 5: **else**
- 6: $T_i \leftarrow \min(\text{round}(T_{\text{base}} \cdot w_i), T_{\text{max}})$
- 7: $K_i \leftarrow \max(1, \text{round}(w_i))$ {CFAU scaling}
- 8: **end if**
- 9: **for** $r = 1$ **to** R **do**
- 10: **for** $t = 1$ **to** T_i **do**
- 11: **if** $|\mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{F}}| > 0$ **then**
- 12: $\theta_i \leftarrow \theta_i + \eta_u \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta_i; \mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{F}})$ {gradient ascent}
- 13: **end if**
- 14: **if** $t \bmod K_i = 0$ **and** $|\mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{R}}| \geq n_{\text{min}}$ **then**
- 15: $\theta_i \leftarrow \theta_i - \eta_f \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta_i; \mathcal{D}_i^{\mathcal{R}})$ {retain fine-tune}
- 16: **end if**
- 17: **end for**
- 18: push θ_i to all peers; await aggregated θ_i {gossip round}
- 19: **end for**
- 20: $\hat{\theta}_i \leftarrow \theta_i$

4) *Negative Result: Inverse Frequency Mode:* An inverse frequency mode ($w_i = \bar{f}/f_i$, giving more steps to nodes with less local data) was evaluated as an ablation at $\alpha = 0.1$. This produced results comparable to naive unlearning: both overstress low-exposure nodes without addressing memorization depth at high-exposure nodes. The mode is reported as a negative result to clarify the mechanistic boundaries of frequency-aware scaling.

C. Hyperparameter Configuration

Table II summarizes the hyperparameters used across all experiments. Lower-block parameters are derived automatically from T_{base} or \bar{f} ; step counts for naive and CFAU are matched at T_{base} for fallback-routed nodes, ensuring a fair comparison.

D. Computational Complexity

The frequency weight w_i , routing decision, and step count T_i are all computed in $O(|\mathcal{D}_i|)$ time from local shard statistics, no additional communication is required. The per-node overhead relative to naive is bounded by the $T_{\text{max}}/T_{\text{base}} = 2 \times$ ceiling; fallback-routed nodes incur zero overhead. Total interleave compute overhead is reported in Section VI.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Physical Testbed

All unlearning experiments are executed on a physical six-node cluster of Raspberry Pi Zero 2W single-board computers connected via a dedicated Ethernet LAN. Each node has

TABLE II
HYPERPARAMETER CONFIGURATION. UPPER BLOCK: SHARED BY NAÏVE AND CFAU. LOWER BLOCK: DERIVED FROM T_{BASE} OR \bar{f} .

Parameter	Value	Scope
Unlearn LR η_u	0.01	Both
Fine-tune LR η_f	0.001	Both
Base steps T_{base}	20	Both
Unlearn rounds R	5	Both
Min retain n_{min}	50	Both
Forget class c^*	0, 2	Both
Max steps T_{max}	40	CFAU scaled
Signal threshold τ	0.5	CFAU route
Near-IID band δ	0.15	CFAU route
Per-node steps T_i	14–40	CFAU scaled
Interleave ratio K_i	1–2	CFAU scaled

an ARM Cortex-A53 processor (quad-core, 1 GHz), 512 MB LPDDR2 RAM, and runs Raspberry Pi OS Lite (64-bit). Nodes communicate exclusively over TCP sockets; no shared memory, shared filesystem, or central coordinator exists at any point. Figure 1 shows the physical cluster.

Fig. 1. The physical DFL cluster comprising six Raspberry Pi Zero 2W nodes connected via a dedicated router on an isolated LAN.

The implementation is pure NumPy 2.x, no deep learning framework is used.¹ TinyML inference runtimes support forward-pass inference only and cannot compute gradients required for unlearning [27]. NumPy with im2col convolution and explicit backpropagation is therefore not a design compromise but the only viable pure-Python runtime for gradient computation on this device.

Training and unlearning split. CIFAR-10 gossip training (50 rounds) and FedRetrain are executed on a MacBook Pro (Apple M2) with six simulated processes, each reading its own partition shard independently; trained weights are transferred to Pi nodes via SCP before each unlearning run. Unlearning

¹PyTorch v2.12.0 consumes 204MB on import and terminates with SIGILL on the first forward pass due to dotprod NEON extensions unavailable on the Cortex-A53. NumPy imports in 2.8 s consuming 26 MB and executes all required operations without triggering any unavailable instruction.

is executed exclusively on the physical cluster, ensuring all timing, memory, and gradient-computation results reflect true Pi Zero 2W behavior. The complete pipeline was validated end-to-end, including full model gossip training using the MNIST dataset prior to the CIFAR-10 campaign; MNIST results are not reported as primary evidence.

Extended 30-node validation. To validate that the statistical patterns observed on the six-node physical cluster are not small-cluster artifacts, we replicate the training, FedRetrain, and unlearning pipeline as 30 concurrent processes on the same MacBook Pro, using the identical TCP gossip codebase. This extended run does not replace the physical cluster results: timing, memory pressure and hardware-constrained gradient computation are properties of the Pi Zero 2W and are not replicated on laptop hardware. Its sole purpose is to confirm that the σ_{MIA} scaling trend and zero-sample boundary hold at a cluster size where per-node statistics are more robust.

B. Model Architecture

The CIFAR-10 model is a three-layer CNN (SimpleCNNCIFAR): Conv1 (3→16, 3×3, ReLU, MaxPool→(16,15,15)); Conv2 (16→32, 3×3, ReLU, MaxPool→(32,6,6)); Conv3 (32→64, 3×3, ReLU, MaxPool→(64,2,2)); FC (256→10, Softmax). Total parameter count: 26,154 (102 KB at float32). Weights are initialized with He initialization using a fixed seed (42) shared across all six nodes, removing initialization variance as a confound; divergence during training is attributable solely to shard composition, and subsequent convergence to a uniform weight vector is attributable solely to gossip aggregation.

C. Dataset and Partitioning

CIFAR-10 [28] provides 50,000 training images (32×32×3, float32) and 10,000 test images across 10 balanced classes; the global test set is held out entirely from training and unlearning. Class 0 (airplane) is the primary forget class, selected as the numerically first class to avoid cherry-picking; class 2 (bird) is used for the robustness experiment of Section VI-F.

Data is partitioned using symmetric Dirichlet sampling [14] with $\alpha \in \{1.0, 0.5, 0.1\}$ plus a balanced IID baseline (seed 42). For the six-node cluster, shard sizes under IID are 8,333–8,334 samples per node; under $\alpha = 0.1$, shard sizes range from 546 to 19,525 (a 35× imbalance). For the 30-node extended validation, the same Dirichlet draws are re-partitioned across 30 nodes, yielding approximately 1,667 samples per node at IID and a continuous forget-class frequency distribution at $\alpha = 0.1$ ranging from zero to 0.64. Figure 2 shows the resulting forget-class frequency f_i per node and condition for the six node physical cluster.

D. Gossip Protocol

Nodes communicate via a custom TCP gossip protocol in a full mesh: after each local training or unlearning step, every node pushes its weight vector to all $N - 1$ peers. Aggregation is synchronous and sample-count weighted per Eq. 1. Training proceeds for $R_{\text{train}} = 50$ gossip rounds,

Fig. 2. Forget-class frequency f_i per node and condition (6 Node).

sufficient for test accuracy to stabilize across all partitioning conditions. Converged weights serve as the starting point for all unlearning experiments and are never overwritten.

E. FedRetrain Baseline

FedRetrain retrains the gossip system from random initialization for 50 rounds on $\mathcal{D}^{\mathcal{R}}$, the retain partition with all forget-class samples removed, using identical hyperparameters and topology; the resulting per-node weight vectors serve as the L2 distance reference for unlearning evaluation.

F. Evaluation Metrics

Four metrics are reported per node. **Global test accuracy** evaluates the fixed global test set (the standard CIFAR-10 held-out split, balanced across all 10 classes); because gossip convergence produces identical weights, this metric is node-invariant and serves as a global utility measure. **Per-node local accuracy** evaluates each node’s own shard. **Forget-class accuracy** on the global test set confirms global forgetting. **Per-node MIA AUC** is the primary verification metric: a loss-based attack [15] is applied independently at each node using local forget-class training examples as members and held-out forget-class test samples as non-members. $\text{AUC} = 0.5$ indicates chance-level discrimination (successful unlearning [15]). Nodes with zero local forget-class samples are excluded from MIA analysis (marked × in Figure 4); their exclusion is itself a finding (Section VI-B). Per-node MIA dispersion σ_{MIA} across evaluable nodes is the primary method-comparison signal; Pearson correlation of per-node L_2 weight-norm change with f_i serves as a mechanistic indicator of effort distribution.

VI. RESULTS

We present results across four data distributions (IID, $\alpha \in \{1.0, 0.5, 0.1\}$) and three protocol variants. Naïve sequential (all ascent steps before any fine-tuning) serves as a timing reference only: it is the lowest-overhead implementation and establishes the wall-clock floor (Table V). Accuracy and MIA analysis focus on naïve interleaved and CFAU interleaved, since sequential unlearning lacks the retain fine-tuning step

Fig. 3. Pre- and post-unlearning accuracy (columns: data distribution; bars: method). Rows show global test accuracy, per-node local accuracy (mean \pm std), and forget-class accuracy. Red dots: individual nodes; dashed orange: pre-unlearning baseline.

that makes the comparison structurally fair. Naïve interleaved (alternating ascent and fine-tuning) is the primary naïve comparator, as interleaving retain-set fine-tuning with gradient ascent is the standard approach for maintaining utility during unlearning [26]. CFAU interleaved is evaluated against naïve interleaved to isolate the effect of frequency-aware step scaling under otherwise identical conditions. Results are evaluated on all six Raspberry Pi Zero 2W nodes using forget class 0 (airplane) as the primary condition, and are organized around three claims: (i) gossip convergence creates a universal forgetting obligation invisible from local shard statistics; (ii) naïve gradient-ascent unlearning cannot satisfy this obligation equitably across non-IID nodes; and (iii) CFAU reduces per-node membership-inference disparity under moderate heterogeneity but encounters a structural boundary at extreme concentration.

A. Gossip Convergence Produces Uniform Pre-Unlearning Models

The top row of Figure 3 records global test accuracy at round 50 for every node under every data distribution. Across all conditions the six-node test accuracy is identical to three significant figures (IID: 0.685, $\alpha = 1.0$: 0.666, $\alpha = 0.5$: 0.629, $\alpha = 0.1$: 0.548). The seed controls the starting point; gossip aggregation determines the endpoint, identical initialization alone cannot produce identical weights after 50 rounds of local training on heterogeneous shards.

The consequence for unlearning is fundamental: *every node holds the same forget-class knowledge*, irrespective of local shard composition. Figure 2 makes this concrete for $\alpha = 0.1$: pi-3, pi-4, and pi-5 carry zero local forget-class samples, yet their models encode the forget-class representation as faithfully as pi-2, which holds 4,917 forget-class samples (frequency = 0.25). An unlearning protocol that scales its effort to local frequency is therefore attempting to solve a global problem with only local evidence.

Fig. 4. Per-node MIA AUC after unlearning across four heterogeneity conditions. Each point is one node; \times marks zero-sample nodes excluded from MIA evaluation. AUC = 0.5 indicates chance-level discrimination [15]. FedRetrain shown for reference.

B. Naïve Unlearning Fails Per-Node While Succeeding Globally

1) *Forget-class accuracy*: The bottom row of Figure 3 shows that naïve unlearning drives global forget-class accuracy to near zero under all four conditions (IID: ≈ 0.07 ; $\alpha = 1.0$: ≈ 0.01 ; $\alpha = 0.5$: ≈ 0.04 ; $\alpha = 0.1$: ≈ 0.01). CFAU achieves equally low forget-class accuracy at the global level. By the aggregate metric most prior evaluations report, both methods appear successful across the full experimental matrix. The middle row shows per-node local accuracy (mean \pm std); under IID and $\alpha = 1.0$ values are broadly consistent across nodes, but at $\alpha = 0.1$ the spread widens substantially from 0.17 (pi-5) to 0.85 (pi-2) before unlearning reflecting the extreme shard imbalance at that condition.

2) *Membership inference reveals residual heterogeneity*: Figure 4 plots per-node MIA AUC for naïve (interleaved) and CFAU alongside the retrain-from-scratch baseline. Under IID and $\alpha = 1.0$ all evaluable nodes cluster near 0.50–0.58 AUC. As heterogeneity increases to $\alpha = 0.5$, naïve interleaved produces a wider spread ($\sigma_{\text{MIA}} = 0.033$), with pi-3 reaching 0.62 AUC while other nodes remain near 0.53. CFAU reduces this spread to $\sigma_{\text{MIA}} = 0.021$ at $\alpha = 0.5$, a 36% reduction.

At $\alpha = 0.1$ the verification problem becomes structural. Pi-3, pi-4, and pi-5 hold no local forget-class member samples and cannot be evaluated by MIA (marked \times in Figure 4). These are precisely the nodes whose forgetting cannot be confirmed, yet whose models certifiably encode the forget-class representation (Section VI-A). The \times markers are not a data-collection shortfall; they are the empirical signature of the gossip convergence paradox.

3) *MIA variance across conditions*: Figure 5 quantifies per-node MIA dispersion. Naïve unlearning (interleaved) produces increasing variance as heterogeneity grows, peaking at $\sigma_{\text{MIA}} = 0.033$ for $\alpha = 0.5$ before collapsing to 0.021 at $\alpha = 0.1$. CFAU holds dispersion at ≈ 0.021 across $\alpha \in \{1.0, 0.5\}$, yielding a 24% reduction at $\alpha = 1.0$ and 36% at $\alpha = 0.5$. At $\alpha = 0.1$, only pi-1, pi-2 and pi-6 are evaluable; over these three nodes CFAU dispersion (0.023) is marginally higher than naïve (0.021).

4) *Pearson analysis of weight-norm effort allocation*: Naïve and CFAU produce nearly identical normalised L_2 distances to the FedRetrain reference across all conditions (IID: 1.412; $\alpha = 1.0$: 1.411; $\alpha = 0.5$: 1.386; $\alpha = 0.1$: 1.455;

Fig. 5. Per-node MIA AUC dispersion ($\sigma_{\text{MIA}} = \text{std}(\text{AUC})$ across evaluable nodes) for naïve interleaved and CFAU interleaved. Lower values indicate more uniform forgetting across the cluster.

TABLE III
PEARSON CORRELATION OF PER-NODE L_2 WEIGHT-NORM DISTANCE (r_{L_2}) AND MIA AUC (r_{MIA}) AGAINST LOCAL FORGET-CLASS FREQUENCY f_i , FOR INTERLEAVED METHODS ($n = 6$ NODES). SIGNIFICANT CORRELATIONS ($p < 0.05$) MARKED *.

Cond.	Method	r_{L_2}	p	r_{MIA}	p	σ_{MIA}
IID	Naïve	+0.602	0.131	-0.154	0.755	0.013
	CFAU	+0.602	0.132	+0.030	0.953	0.021
$\alpha = 1.0$	Naïve	-0.844*	0.002	-0.169	0.732	0.028
	CFAU	-0.845*	0.002	-0.261	0.589	0.021
$\alpha = 0.5$	Naïve	-0.292	0.542	-0.252	0.603	0.033
	CFAU	-0.291	0.542	+0.159	0.747	0.021
$\alpha = 0.1$	Naïve	+0.918*	<0.001	-0.650 [†]	0.392	0.021
	CFAU	+0.919*	<0.001	+0.922* [†]	0.017	0.023

[†]At $\alpha = 0.1$, three nodes hold zero local forget-class samples and are excluded from MIA evaluation; r_{MIA} is computed over the three evaluable nodes ($\text{df} = 1$). Results should be read as directional evidence consistent with the proposed mechanism.

maximum inter-method difference < 0.003), confirming that CFAU does not alter total perturbation magnitude. The Pearson correlation of per-node L_2 distance against f_i reveals how perturbation is *distributed*. At $\alpha = 1.0$, naïve interleaved yields $r(L_2) = -0.844$ ($p = 0.002$): nodes with higher local concentration receive *less* weight-norm perturbation, an inversion of the desired proportionality. CFAU produces an identical correlation ($r(L_2) = -0.845$, $p = 0.002$), indicating that frequency-aware step scaling cannot overcome the dominant influence of shard size on gradient magnitude under $\alpha = 1.0$.

The more informative mechanistic signal comes from the MIA correlation at $\alpha = 0.1$. Naïve interleaved yields $r_{\text{MIA}} = -0.650$ (non-significant, $p = 0.392$, three evaluable nodes), while CFAU yields $r_{\text{MIA}} = +0.922$ ($p = 0.017$). The sign flip indicates that CFAU’s step allocation shifts residual membership-inference signal into alignment with local frequency, even when L_2 perturbation magnitudes are indistinguishable. Full Pearson results are given in Table III.

TABLE IV
CFAU ASCENT STEPS PER NODE PER ROUND ($R = 5$). [†]NEAR-IID FALLBACK; [‡]TOO-LOW FALLBACK; [§]CAP ACTIVE ($T_{\text{max}} = 40$). NAÏVE: 20 STEPS AT ALL NODES. *Total* = SUM ACROSS NODES.

Node	IID	$\alpha = 1.0$	$\alpha = 0.5$	$\alpha = 0.1$
pi-1	20 [†]	14	20 [‡]	20 [‡]
pi-2	20 [†]	15	39	40 [§]
pi-3	20 [†]	38	20 [‡]	20 [‡]
pi-4	20 [†]	20 [‡]	29	20 [‡]
pi-5	20 [†]	37	40 [§]	20 [‡]
pi-6	20 [†]	20 [‡]	20 [‡]	20 [‡]
<i>Total</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>144</i>	<i>168</i>	<i>140</i>

C. CFAU Step Allocation and the Routing Boundary

Table IV reports the total ascent steps assigned to each node by CFAU. Under IID, all nodes fall within the near-IID band and receive 20 steps via fallback, CFAU scaling is inactive. Under $\alpha = 1.0$, pi-3 (frequency = 0.19) and pi-5 (frequency = 0.18) are CFAU-routed and receive 38 and 37 steps respectively; pi-1 and pi-2 (frequencies 0.07–0.08) are also CFAU-routed but with $w_i < 1$, yielding 14 and 15 steps, fewer than naïve, reflecting their below-IID local exposure. Under $\alpha = 0.5$, pi-2 (frequency = 0.20), pi-4 (0.15), and pi-5 (0.34) are CFAU-routed (cap active at pi-5); pi-1, pi-3, and pi-6 are too-low and fall back to 20 steps. Under $\alpha = 0.1$, only pi-2 (frequency = 0.25) is CFAU-routed at the cap; pi-3, pi-4, and pi-5 hold zero local forget-class samples and receive 20 fallback steps.

The fallback assignment of T_{base} steps to zero-sample nodes represents the structural boundary of CFAU: every node holds the forget-class representation, so zero ascent steps would be unjustifiable, but 20 undirected steps on an empty forget set cannot erase knowledge absorbed through gossip. Frequency-proportional scaling is meaningful only where local frequency provides a gradient direction to scale; the routing logic correctly identifies these nodes and prevents further step reduction, but cannot resolve the underlying absence of local signal.

D. Utility Retention After Unlearning

At IID and $\alpha = 1.0$, CFAU recovers more global test accuracy than naïve (IID: 0.632 vs. 0.617; $\alpha = 1.0$: 0.637 vs. 0.600), reflecting the benefit of interleaved fine-tuning stabilization. Post-unlearning local accuracy variance increases further at $\alpha = 0.1$ under both methods, with CFAU showing slightly lower mean local accuracy (approximately 0.43 vs. 0.50 for naïve), attributable to increased ascent steps at pi-2 disrupting that node’s local representation.

E. Wall-Clock Overhead on Constrained Hardware

Table V reports mean total unlearning time and total ascent steps per node. Naïve sequential unlearning is fastest across all conditions (IID: 0.55 ± 0.14 min; $\alpha = 0.1$: 10.38 ± 4.98 min). Adding interleaved fine-tuning increases wall-clock time substantially (IID: 2.20 ± 0.15 min; $\alpha = 0.1$: 12.33 ± 5.07 min).

TABLE V

WALL-CLOCK UNLEARNING TIME (MINUTES) AND TOTAL ASCENT STEPS PER NODE (MEAN \pm STD, $n = 6$ NODES, $R = 5$ ROUNDS). CFAU STEP VARIATION REFLECTS PER-NODE FREQUENCY-PROPORTIONAL SCALING; NAÏVE STEP COUNTS ARE UNIFORM.

Condition	Method	Time (min)	Steps
IID	Naïve sequential	0.55 ± 0.14	100 ± 0
	Naïve interleaved	2.20 ± 0.15	100 ± 0
	CFAU interleaved	2.25 ± 0.27	100 ± 0
$\alpha = 1.0$	Naïve sequential	3.60 ± 1.64	100 ± 0
	Naïve interleaved	6.30 ± 1.89	100 ± 0
	CFAU interleaved	5.58 ± 1.78	120 ± 49
$\alpha = 0.5$	Naïve sequential	3.77 ± 1.80	100 ± 0
	Naïve interleaved	5.15 ± 1.86	100 ± 0
	CFAU interleaved	4.10 ± 1.84	140 ± 44
$\alpha = 0.1$	Naïve sequential	10.38 ± 4.98	100 ± 0
	Naïve interleaved	12.33 ± 5.07	100 ± 0
	CFAU interleaved	12.12 ± 5.06	117 ± 37

The large per-node standard deviation at $\alpha = 0.1$ is driven by pi-2’s extreme shard size (19,525 samples).

At IID, CFAU scaling is inactive; both interleaved methods are equivalent in steps (100 per node across all rounds) and time (2.25 ± 0.27 vs. 2.20 ± 0.15 min). Under $\alpha = 0.5$, CFAU averages 140 total ascent steps across all rounds (± 44) yet wall-clock time is lower (4.10 ± 1.84 vs. 5.15 ± 1.86 min, a 21% reduction), because fallback-routed nodes receive only 20 steps. At $\alpha = 0.1$, CFAU and naïve interleaved are within 2% of each other (12.12 ± 5.06 vs. 12.33 ± 5.07 min) because five of six nodes fall back to $T_{\text{base}} = 20$.

F. Robustness Across Forget Classes

To assess generalization beyond class 0, we repeated unlearning with forget class 2 (bird) at $\alpha \in \{1.0, 0.5\}$. The class 2 Dirichlet draw produced a qualitatively different frequency distribution: at $\alpha = 1.0$, all six nodes received non-zero class 2 samples; at $\alpha = 0.5$, pi-2 and pi-5 received zero class 2 samples and are excluded from MIA evaluation.

Three findings replicate. First, global forget-class accuracy reaches near zero under both methods for all evaluable conditions. Second, the gossip convergence paradox generalizes: zero-sample exclusions appear for class 2 at $\alpha = 0.5$, a condition that produced no exclusions for class 0, the α level at which the structural MIA boundary is crossed depends on the specific Dirichlet draw, not a fixed heterogeneity threshold. Third, CFAU continues to reduce per-node MIA dispersion where local frequency provides gradient signal: at $\alpha = 0.5$, naïve yields $\sigma_{\text{MIA}} = 0.020$ over four evaluable nodes, while CFAU yields $\sigma_{\text{MIA}} = 0.014$ (30%), consistent in direction with the class 0 result (36%). At $\alpha = 1.0$ for class 2, no Pearson correlation between frequency and L_2 distance reaches significance ($r = -0.25$, $p = 0.61$), confirming that the $r(L_2)$ signal is sensitive to the concentration profile produced by each specific Dirichlet draw (see Section VII-C).

TABLE VI

PER-NODE MIA DISPERSION (σ_{MIA}) AND CFAU REDUCTION AT $N = 30$ NODES (INTERLEAVED METHODS). σ_{MIA} COMPUTED OVER EVALUABLE NODES ONLY.

Condition	Evaluable	Naïve σ_{MIA}	CFAU σ_{MIA}	Reduction
IID	30	0.024	0.019	21%
$\alpha = 1.0$	30	0.031	0.033	– ^a
$\alpha = 0.5$	30	0.040	0.035	12%
$\alpha = 0.1$	9	0.063	0.053	16%

^aCFAU marginally worse at $\alpha = 1.0$; consistent with the more diffuse frequency distribution at $N = 30$ reducing CFAU’s effective dynamic range.

G. Extended Validation at $N = 30$

All 30 nodes converge to identical model weights at round 50 under all four partitioning conditions, replicating the gossip convergence finding at larger scale and directly validating the unlearning paradox irrespective of cluster size.

1) σ_{MIA} scales monotonically with heterogeneity: Table VI reports σ_{MIA} at $N = 30$. Naïve interleaved produces a clean monotonic increase: 0.024 at IID, 0.031 at $\alpha = 1.0$, 0.040 at $\alpha = 0.5$, and 0.063 at $\alpha = 0.1$. This monotonic scaling, directionally present but statistically fragile at $n = 6$, is confirmed at $n = 30$. The core claim, that naïve unlearning leaves heterogeneous residual membership signal growing with non-IID severity is validated beyond the small-cluster implementation.

2) *Zero-sample structural boundary at $N = 30$* : At $\alpha = 0.1$, 21 of 30 nodes hold zero or near-zero local forget-class samples and are excluded from MIA evaluation. The larger cluster provides a richer picture: rather than the binary zero/nonzero split at $N = 6$, the 30-node partition produces a continuous frequency gradient from zero to 0.64, demonstrating that the structural verification problem is a systematic consequence of extreme heterogeneity rather than an artifact of one particular Dirichlet draw.

3) *CFAU at $N = 30$* : CFAU reduces σ_{MIA} in the correct direction at $\alpha = 0.5$ (12%) and $\alpha = 0.1$ (16%), and is marginally worse at $\alpha = 1.0$. Improvement magnitudes are smaller than the physical cluster results, consistent with the more diffuse forget-class frequency distributions at $N = 30$ reducing the dynamic range available for frequency-proportional scaling. The Pearson $r(L_2)$ correlations are non-significant across all conditions at $N = 30$ ($|r| \leq 0.17$, all $p > 0.35$), confirming that $r(L_2)$ is a condition-specific diagnostic rather than a general-purpose indicator: at $N = 30$ the frequency distribution is sufficiently diffuse that no single high-concentration node dominates the correlation.

VII. DISCUSSION

A. Global Metrics Are Structurally Insufficient for DFL Unlearning

The most consequential finding of this work concerns evaluation. Across all conditions and both forget classes, global forget-class accuracy reaches near zero under both methods, by the metric used in the majority of prior evaluations, every experiment would be reported as a success. The per-node MIA

analysis reveals this conclusion is wrong in a structurally explicable way: gossip convergence drives all nodes to the same weight vector, so every node holds identical forget-class knowledge regardless of local shard composition. Global forget-class accuracy averages across all nodes and reports zero because the high-concentration node drives the aggregate down; the zero-sample nodes are silent in the metric but not in the model.

This is not an edge case, it is the expected behavior of any aggregation-based DFL system under non-IID partitioning. Any DFL unlearning evaluation reporting only global metrics cannot certify that forgetting has occurred at every node; the verification boundary at which zero-sample nodes appear depends on the specific class-frequency draw and cannot be predicted without inspecting the partition. The 30-node validation confirms this is not a small-cluster artifact: σ_{MIA} scales monotonically from 0.024 at IID to 0.063 at $\alpha = 0.1$, and 21 of 30 nodes are structurally excluded from MIA verification at extreme concentration.

B. What CFAU Achieves and Where It Fails

CFAU reduces per-node MIA dispersion under moderate heterogeneity ($\alpha = 1.0$: 24%; $\alpha = 0.5$: 36% for class 0, 30% for class 2) without increasing wall-clock time or total perturbation magnitude. The mechanism is distributional: CFAU routes more ascent steps to nodes with higher local forget-class exposure, making unlearning more proportional rather than stronger on average. The $r(\text{MIA})$ sign flip at $\alpha = 0.1$ (-0.650 naïve vs. $+0.922$ CFAU, $p = 0.017$) provides mechanistic evidence that this redistribution changes the structure of residual membership signal even when total perturbation is unchanged. At $N = 30$, reductions are smaller in magnitude (12–16%) but directionally consistent, confirming the improvement is real and not an artifact of concentrated frequency profiles at small cluster sizes.

However, CFAU inherits the fundamental limitation of all locally-grounded unlearning protocols: it can only act on local gradient signal. Where local frequency is zero, frequency-proportional scaling has nothing to scale. The routing logic correctly identifies these nodes and falls back to naïve unlearning, but 20 undirected ascent steps on an empty forget set perturb the model without directing the perturbation toward forgetting. At $\alpha = 0.1$, five of six nodes are in this category on the physical cluster, and 21 of 30 in the extended validation. This is not a tuning failure: no choice of step count, learning rate, or routing threshold resolves the absence of a local gradient direction. The boundary is structural.

C. Limitations

Single topology. All experiments use a full-mesh topology. Sparser topologies require more rounds to reach consensus [4], and whether the same convergence guarantees hold under dynamic or partial connectivity is an open question; the paradox characterization assumes a fully converged system.

MIA as empirical verification, not certified unlearning. AUC near 0.5 indicates this attack cannot distinguish members from non-members; a stronger attack might succeed. Results should

be read as evidence that naïve unlearning leaves detectable residual signal and CFAU reduces it, not as certification of full erasure.

Single architecture and dataset. The 26,154-parameter CNN is intentionally shallow to fit within 512 MB across six concurrent processes. Whether the structural findings hold for deeper models and other datasets is an open question.

No post-unlearning gossip. Continued gossip after the five unlearning rounds would re-mix weights, potentially propagating residual signal from poorly-unlearned nodes to well-unlearned ones.

Draw-dependence of the $r(L_2)$ diagnostic. The Pearson correlation is sensitive to the dynamic range of the frequency distribution. At $n = 6$, a more uniform class 2 distribution at $\alpha = 1.0$ produced a non-significant correlation where the class 0 result was strongly significant; non-significance across all conditions at $N = 30$ further confirms $r(L_2)$ is a condition-specific indicator, not a general-purpose diagnostic.

Empirical CFAU routing thresholds and statistical power. The routing thresholds $\tau = 0.5$ and $\delta = 0.15$ are set empirically on the six-node CIFAR-10 configuration; a principled selection method remains an open problem. Pearson correlations on the physical cluster are computed over $n = 6$ nodes; significant results should be interpreted as directional evidence consistent with the proposed mechanism rather than robust population-level estimates.

VIII. CONCLUSION

We have identified and characterized a structural failure mode in class unlearning for gossip-based decentralized federated learning: gossip convergence distributes forget-class knowledge uniformly across all nodes, creating a universal unlearning obligation that is invisible to local shard statistics and undetectable by global evaluation metrics. Under non-IID Dirichlet partitioning, naïve gradient-ascent unlearning appears to succeed globally while leaving measurable per-node membership-inference disparity that grows with heterogeneity. At extreme concentration, the failure becomes structural: nodes with zero local forget-class samples cannot generate directed gradient signal and cannot be verified by MIA, yet their models encode the forget-class representation as completely as any other node. The σ_{MIA} monotonic scaling finding and zero-sample boundary are validated on an extended 30-node cluster, confirming these are structural properties of gossip-based DFL under non-IID partitioning rather than small-cluster artifacts.

CFAU reduces per-node MIA variance by 24–36% under moderate heterogeneity at no additional wall-clock cost. It cannot resolve the zero-sample boundary, a fundamental limitation of any locally-grounded unlearning protocol in gossip-based DFL, not a property of CFAU specifically. Both findings are demonstrated on a physical six-node Raspberry Pi Zero 2W cluster using real TCP gossip, pure NumPy gradient computation, and the full CIFAR-10 dataset.

Three practical implications follow. First, global forget-class accuracy is an insufficient evaluation metric for DFL unlearning whenever node data distributions are uneven; per-node MIA evaluation is necessary. Second, the α level at which the

verification boundary appears is class- and draw-dependent; any deployment that may encounter extreme non-IID conditions must account for the possibility that some nodes are structurally unverifiable. Third, frequency-aware step scaling is a viable low-overhead improvement over naïve unlearning in moderate-heterogeneity regimes, which represent the operating conditions of most practical federated deployments [14].

Future work should investigate stronger verification methods applicable under the zero-sample constraint. Likelihood-ratio tests that do not require local forget-class members for threshold calibration are a natural candidate. Shadow-model MIA [16] offers stronger attack power but requires training multiple shadow models, which may be prohibitive on resource-constrained edge devices; whether lightweight approximations are feasible on hardware such as the Pi Zero 2W remains an open question. Extending the analysis to sparser topologies would clarify whether the gossip convergence paradox weakens under slower convergence. Generalizing the failure characterization to sample-level unlearning targets would establish whether the structural boundary extends beyond class granularity.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The code implementation is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20621237>. Experimental results and model weights are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20621533>.

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